

SPECIFIC STRUCTURE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORICAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND HISTORICAL THINKING IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the structural foundations of the development of historical consciousness and historical thought, its structure, content, synthesis of practical skills formed on the basis of educational and educational tools that develop it, scientific views of educators, sociologists, Methodist scientists and psychologists, and highlights the means of pedagogical influence of subjective attitude towards them.*

Keywords: *historical consciousness, historical thinking, specific features, the basis of the structure, the content of development, the conceptual basis, the component, the synthesis of developing educational and educational tools, practical skills.*

СПЕЦИФИЧЕСКАЯ СТРУКТУРА РАЗВИТИЯ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО СОЗНАНИЯ И ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ У УЧАЩИХСЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются структурные основы развития исторического сознания и исторического мышления, его структура, содержание, синтез практических навыков, формируемых на основе развивающих его учебно-воспитательных средств, научные взгляды педагогов, социологов, методистов и психологов, освещаются средства педагогического воздействия субъективного отношения к ним.*

Ключевые слова: *историческое сознание, историческое мышление, специфика, структурная основа, содержание развития, концептуальная основа, компонент, развивающие учебно-воспитательные средства, синтез практических умений и навыков.*

Pedagogical, methodological sociological research of any scientific and social significance involves the study of historical consciousness. Historical consciousness is an integral part of social activity. At the same time, types, forms and stages of development are one of the relatively basic objects of historical science in the study. At the time of historical consciousness, ideas, views, norms, value orientations, relationships are embodied.

In the development of historical consciousness and historical thinking in students of general secondary education schools, the peculiarities of their social concepts with philosophical political, legal, moral rights, religious, aesthetic, scientific proportionality are intertwined with each other.

Realized in the scientific expression of the structural basis of historical consciousness and the complex of various units in it.

The field in the analysis of scientific research of specialists, historical consciousness is interpreted as a synthesis of new knowledge studied as a socio-cultural system and as an environment in which spiritual culture determines the socialization of the individual, the regulation of behavior.

It is from this point of view that it is also the same fact that there is a certain learning problem of historical consciousness as a subjective factor in social practice.

Indeed, how the system of value orientations of the functional social essence of historical consciousness is developed young generation cognitivism subjective attitude of the country's historical past, customs, morality of society to various historical events, correspondence to national and universal values to a certain extent presupposes the acquisition of knowledge. "Historical consciousness is one of the important forms of social consciousness, manifested as the result of the process of perception of the individual. There are a variety of definitions given to the concept of historical consciousness: historical consciousness is the realization that everything, even spiritual existence, has taken place, that is in any knowledge". In the development of historical consciousness and historical thinking in students of general secondary education schools, it is reflected in the independent reading of the cultural heritage of the ancestors in them, its practical application and its strong assimilation and appropriate implementation.

In the historical consciousness there is an internal conflict consisting of "past-today-early". In recognition of this feature, A.X.Samiyev said that "Historical consciousness is the assimilation by Man (social group, Society) of his place in time, the connection of the past with the present and the future. It is a focus on the past that is important for perspective, he expresses"[2]. "Historical consciousness is a feeling that expresses the presence in a person of elements that reflect his thoughts and views about the past. Historical consciousness can also be used as a synonym for historical memory, but in general it is a broader concept, since historical memory as a "spontaneous" phenomenon and as scientific and historical thoughts about the past are embodied in the structure of historical consciousness, that is, historical memory is the core of historical consciousness"[3].

Noted sociologist scholar J.In toshenko's opinion: "if we characterize the content and essence of historical consciousness, it can be said that it is a set of ideas, views, visions, feelings, moods, ideas, which embody the perception and assessment of the past with its entire diversity,

characteristic of society in general, in particular, various socio - demographic, socio-professional and ethno-social groups, as well as individuals”[4].

The formation of historical thinking in students through the means of problematic education can be divided into four levels:

a) independent, traditional historical thought-the historical, fact that the teacher offers, mastering the methods of learning by the student of knowledge, the beginning of independent work by students, limitation to exercises with the property of remembering;

b) semi-independent historical thought is characterized by the participation of students in the application of previously acquired historical knowledge on new topics and the search for ways to solve educational problems;

d) independent historical thinking in this, with the text of the history textbook, the reader himself Works, applies the knowledge gained to new topics, revises, changes, solves problems of moderate complexity, assignments, proves his hypotheses with the help of a little of the teacher;

e) creative historical thinking requires discovery and creative activity, such as creative, requiring logical thinking, logical analysis, comparison, finding new ways to solve educational problems, independent proof, drawing independent conclusions, generalization[5].

A high indicator of the level of development of historical consciousness arises from the structure of complex processes of a regional scale, the socio-cultural development of modern societies, the history, a comprehensive interpretation of today's day and the future prospects for social progress, national values increase its interest in improvement.

The process of development of historical consciousness is justified in the fact that readers understand the content of axiological approaches and understand the reasons for the emergence of historical events, and have visions for them. The connection of historical consciousness with the past is manifested in the sum of the relations between history and the future. So, we cannot say that the problem of the development of historical consciousness in Readers has arisen quite recently. The analysis of scientific-theoretical studies shows that interest in the solution of this problem has always increased. In other words, historical consciousness is expressed as a condition for the self-identification of society and man. In this, the focus on the knowledge of the world in the content of the development of historical consciousness, the study of the expression of socio-cultural and historicism from the essence of the given context is characterized in the proportion of the goals that develop Man and society.

The development of historical consciousness relies on the basic methodological guidelines with which various historical periods are defined, which must first include the philosophical meaning and interpretation of the basic concepts of consciousness and history.

The philosophical reflection of historical consciousness makes it possible to form a general concept of historicism, the value characteristic of the position of this consciousness worldview and the relevance of human life as a social basis.

There are many views, approaches and models of scientists who have studied historical consciousness. Definitions of the term "historical consciousness" in the scientific literature are a phenomenon of understanding the nature and genesis of its occurrence. In particular, the identification of historical consciousness through cognitivism is known as objective reality-the subjectivity of the connoisseur; in the attitude to the subject through ideal activity is considered as a complex organized material system.

Later scientific and methodological sources explain that in the definition of historical consciousness, the content of consciousness as a spiritual and practical phenomenon, ideas and theories are increasing. In this, the role of the informative approach and the priority of the information and communication model allow the processes underlying the definition of historical consciousness, the methodology for its development, the evidence of knowledge obtained as a result of the mental activity of the subject to be clear and meaningful.

In schools of general secondary education, the development of historical consciousness and historical thinking of students contributes to the growth of axiological approaches to the study of cultural heritage in them. In them, feelings of humanity, patriotism, respect for national values are absorbed, professional and colloquial skills are activated. It acts as a complex and methodically important spiritual and practical phenomenon in modern social life and requires taking into account all the conditions and factors in its study. In the context of the use of historical experience, its active influence on its activities, historical consciousness as a whole for the progressive development of Man and society is synthesized by the method of scientific knowledge and research of almost all aspects of social life.

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